

MANUSCRIPTS OF THE WORK "BABURNAMA"

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Abstract : This in the article Zahiriddin mUhammad Babur's work " Baburnoma " in Russia and in Uzbekistan stored of manuscripts the most famous copies about around information given

Key words : A. Beveridge , copy of Kerr , Senkovsky copy , Khiva copies , Tashkent copies , Saint- Petersburg , Kazan lithograph .

"Baburnama" of the East the most masterpiece from his works that it was because of , written from the period starting from different to languages translation and of his work manuscripts wide spreads . There is of copies most of them in the 17th and 18th centuries different people by moved from them most of them are in St. Petersburg , the rest Calcutta , Delhi , Agra, Hyderabad , India , Manchester , London, Edinburgh, Tashkent and another in cities is stored . But this manuscripts so far each other with comparatively unstudied . In them differences showed without of the work scientific and critical the text until now created it's not . English Orientalist scientist AS Beveridge and Uzbek scientist Porso Shamsiyev " Baburnoma " manuscripts check and publication reach in the field exploratory work take went even though they are scientific and critical the text to compose good be those who did not receive Only Japanese historian scientist Eiji Mano Hyderabad and Kerr copies by learning critical-comparative the text to create succeeded will be But this the text of " Baburnoma". complete critical the text means created it's not .

The work " Baburnoma ". manuscript copies about in full information English of Orientalist Annette Beveridge to the work dedicated from the articles get can of the work the most a lot spread out manuscript of copies most part in

Russian libraries is being saved . They are St. Petersburg and in Moscow is stored . These are manuscripts volume and content in terms of from each other almost difference does not But each manuscript some advantage and to shortcomings has

Russian Sciences academy Oriental studies Institute St. Petersburg with number 685 in the section of the preserved work " Baburnoma ". manuscript very is characterful . Temur Steel named person to Bukhara in 1714 trip by doing work manuscript to the hand entered and in 1725 to Saint Petersburg take came from Orientalist scientist Copy by G. Y. Kerr in 1737 as copied . From 420 pages consists of was this manuscript complete is Ilminsky to the publication basis has been and e ng unique from manuscripts one is considered In science this copy is called " Kerr copy " ¹. He is black ink with of the sheet one to the side written split , scroll second side Latin to the language tajjima to do for left Kerr copy A. Beveridge by facsimile in case publication done Hyderabad to a copy to compare that's it shows that Kerr copy si his own language features and volume in terms of Hyderabad from the copy won't stay . But on page 188 of Kerr's copy , « Bowsung' ur Mirza own there are many in front Mongolian of a person to the neck from saying next image sheet to the border Persian in the language written Hyderabad in copy while this image Uzbek in the language written From this except , Baburshah from pages 1021 to 1084 in Kerr's copy to the pen special was not there is also history . In this Timur , Shahrukh , Ulug Bek , Abusaid , Sultan Husayn , Sultan Ahmad, Sultan Mahmud, Umarshaikh , Babur mirza (Zahiriddin Babur) and Humayun of the king short-short histories given This history is undoubtedly the next movers by added to be need Such history Hyderabad in copy does not occur .

St. Petersburg State university East manuscripts in the library stored " Fayzikhanov copy "² his own volume and structure in terms of Kerr copy with one is different . From page 331 consists of this manuscript 1255 AH , Sha'ban On the 29th of the month (November 1839) Mulla Faiz Khan by moved being , he first Orientalist scientist Mirza Kozimbek personal in the library saved . of Kozimbek

¹St. Petersburg Oriental studies institute library , inventory No. 685

²St. Petersburg East manuscripts library , inventory No. 3814.

from his death then , in 1871, the university to the library submitted . of the work at the end « Asli in copy full the date 1026 is written . Kerr copy at the end and that's it the date is written as 1126 . That's two 100 years in copy difference of the mover random error to be can Because both a copy to each other to compare to them one manuscript basis that it was shows . St. Petersburg State at the university stored from the Kerr copy of the copy different side that is , from page 224 to page 277, it is reversed attached , and on page 145 big one sentence down the rest Manuscript unfinished is considered

Russian Sciences in St. Petersburg academy Asia in the museum stored " Senkovsky copy ", the work " Baburnoma ". manuscripts inside very is noteworthy . With number 590 stored this manuscript , 1121 Hijri- (1709 AD) , Rajab of the month beginning , Monday day mullah Abdul Wahab read G' ijduvani by in Bukhara writing finished This is a manuscript Senkovsky by Nazarboy in 1824 Turkestan named Bukhara from the merchant buy received Senkovsky a copy disease in his writing written , titles red in ink cities , places and some events name while sheet to the border writing went But do not title most of them Persian in the language

St. Petersburg Saltykov-Shedrin named public in the library Typ.HC.104 number with , conditional as " Khiva called " copy ". manuscript is being saved . From 574 pages consists of this manuscript mover of the person name never where not shown . But mover book at the end this work 1278 Hijri , Zul Hijjah of the month ten at seven , Sunday on (1861) Khaqan ibn al- Khaqan of Hazrat Said Muhammad Khan to the command according to that it has been moved shows . And this work In Khiva that it was moved the conclusion to issue basis will be

Manuscript disease letter with beautiful written , titles red in ink Titles Arabic language with one in line his Uzbek in the language translation with written For example , " **Actually date iho and tis'a mia , ie history of Hijri nine face stain the first year vaqoe** " Kerr and St. Petersburg in this manuscript State of the university in copies there is has been addition history no But the mover Babur

to the language special has been one how much word new words with replaced by : vale - but (p. 10), hiyli - a lot (p. 2), marrow - hand (p. 21), earlier - closer (p. 21), in place - in place (15 page), less sheet yerdur - suyi less will (p. 70) and others Don't be all " Baburnoma". of the mover interference as a result some lexicon to changes from meeting next copies one that shows .

Uzbekistan Republic Sciences of the academy Beruni in the name of Oriental studies institute library H. Sulaiman number 2588 in the fund with stored manuscript . N. Ilminsky in 1880 print based on moved defective copy Number 9377 with stored second one the manuscript was written in 1936 , completed copy is considered This copy is also a row lexicon and morphological in character there are changes . In this institute again Copied in 1908 , number 13 with , from 565 pages consists of manuscript available , but is incomplete .

From the above except Baku and On Monday stored manuscript copies there is .

" Baburnoma " is original text in case the first times Russian Orientalist N. I. Ilminsky by Professor GYKerr a copy based on 1857 in Kazan full publication done English in 1905 Orientalist A. Beveridge of " Boburnoma". in Hyderabad jump in from the museum find a facsimile in syncography publication is enough Hyderabad of a copy moved year and mover known if not , original from the copy or to him closer one from the copy moved known . It is believed that this copy was copied in 1700 will be done . So So we have different types of " Baburnoma". extract copies except Kazan and in London publication done two print to a copy we have

" Baburnoma". unknown one from the copy received fragments the first times in 1705 Vicen by in Amsterdam publication delivered . " Tatars " to him of the country east and north part of it's a joke " definition " is named . J. Leyden , V. Erskin " Boburnoma". Uzbek and Persian copies compared to English to the language translation and published it in ³London in 1826 . This is a translation L.

³Jawaharlal Nehru , India history 9th edition. London, 1905, pp. 429.

W. King by a little completed in London again publication done First English in the language translation A. Kaiser by German for short to the language translation done and in 1828 in Leipzig publication done Pave de Courteil and " Baburnoma". ancient Uzbek from his manuscripts one full in 1871 respectively French to the language taijima in Paris publication did For now orientalists and historians In Kazan and in London pressed this from texts and some in libraries stored from manuscripts using they are coming

Used literature

1. Boburnoma . St. Petersburg . East manuscripts library .
2. St. Petersburg East manuscripts library , inventory No. 3814.

Indian history 9th edition. London, 1905. - B. P. 429.

